

WHAT MAKES OR BREAKS FIELDWORK?: EXPLORING FACTORS WHICH AFFECT
STUDENT EXPERIENCE AND PEDAGOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS

by

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ORCID ID: 0009-0001-3085-255X

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10558576

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton

December 2023

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Date:

01/15/24

1/15/24

Abstract

Fieldwork activities within natural sciences offer numerous student benefits, including solidifying higher-order thinking, transferable skills, and analytical reasoning. Despite the evident benefits of fieldwork which supplement classroom learning, many students have reservations or choose not to participate. An interview and questionnaire were administered to undergraduate students taking the Spring 2023 geological field techniques class at California State University Fullerton. Questions analyzed how perceptions of self-efficacy, identity as a geologist, and sense of belonging changed throughout the class, as well as how comfort and preparedness affected the students' experience. Over 50% of post-course participants mentioned class topics as problematic, stating they would like more guidance on the subjects and assignments. Survey data showed improvement in all geological field techniques and methods, yet some factors related to sense of belonging declined from 94% in pre-course to 75% in post-course. Students expressed concern about knowledge on assignments, what to bring, and the conditions of working outside. Notably, lacking outdoor experience had no adverse effect on students' fieldwork experience; the majority had confidence in instructor preparedness. Students' self-efficacy and identity as a geologist generally positively changed by the end of the course. While students felt confident in the instructors and improved geological techniques, the lack of preparation for working outdoors and feeling lost on assignments negatively impacted their experience. Future renditions of this course and other classes across multiple disciplines can benefit from focusing pre-field class time on preparing for field assignments, situations one may encounter, and how to prepare for them.

Introduction

Fieldwork is an essential component to the study of natural sciences. Especially within the geological sciences, techniques and skills gained through participation greatly enhance students' education no matter their proposed career path (Fig. 1). Despite the importance of fieldwork, students often still have reservations about participating in field-based activities. Students choose not to or are hesitant to participate in the field due to hurdles including: financial costs, physical capabilities, accessibility, location, familial duties, etc. (Boyle et al., 2007; Scott et al., 2012; Scott et al. 2019; Giles et al., 2020). The aspect of being outdoors may prove to be daunting for many, especially if those students are not accustomed to such activities (Scott et al., 2019). These students most likely will not have the proper gear, which may negatively impact their experience in the field (i.e., being too cold, aches), not to mention the additional costs to acquire such gear (Giles et al., 2020).

It is important to address these hurdles because of the apparent benefits that fieldwork provides. One factor attributed to the effectiveness of field learning is the integration of active learning (Jones and Washko, 2021). Adding an active and hands-on approach to the subject matter enables students to fully engage. Field trips often involve exploration in order to collaborate on project-based activities as students develop their own sense of meaning (Jones and Washko, 2021). This allows students to test concepts learned in the classroom environment first-hand, deepening understanding (Dykas and Valentino, 2016; Fleishner et al., 2017). The co-production of knowledge is also a beneficial aspect of fieldwork. Student-instructor relationships are strengthened, further encouraging educational growth outside of the field (Stokes and Boyle, 2009). The setting in which fieldwork is conducted allows professionals within the discipline to influence those who may be in their shoes in the future, fostering a connection between those in-training and those who are established (Mogk and Goodwin, 2012; Jones and Washko, 2021).

Benefits of fieldwork may not be directly apparent to students, therefore Peasland et al. (2021) suggest that highlighting both technical and transferable skill outcomes will help students to make their decision on whether to participate in fieldwork. This is related to the utility value of such work, where participation in field-courses bolsters employability (Peasland et al, 2021; Wall and Speake, 2012). Students may be more likely to participate in fieldwork if they are informed of the transferable skills it offers, presenting a high utility value. Traditionally, field-based coursework is focused on acquiring skills that would be useful in industry jobs, such as mining, but changing times have seen different career paths, such as renewable energies, hire an increasing share of geoscience workers (Giles et al., 2020). While many technical skills are delivered without fieldwork, alternative opportunities may be a more appropriate choice for some students (Peasland et al., 2021). Fieldwork not only allows students to expand their knowledge of a subject matter, but also provides the opportunity to improve soft skills such as communication and collaboration that may not be possible in a classroom environment. Retention within the natural sciences is improved when students feel a sense of belonging (Jones and Washko, 2021).

Statement of Purpose

Geology 380: Field Techniques (GEOL 380) is a required course to earn a Bachelor of Science degree in Geology at California State University, Fullerton (CSUF). This course is meant to form a basis for geological field skills that the student may utilize in a future career.

Furthermore, the higher-order thinking and practice performed throughout this course can solidify other transferable skills, such as team collaboration, analytical reasoning, and adaptability.

Fieldwork for this course is performed on four occasions, with the class intentionally structured to “ease” students into the field. The first field trip was a local day trip where students minimally utilized new techniques, and was also used to form a basis on what to and not to do/bring. The second field trip was a day trip, farther than the first where students deployed new techniques learned in the classroom, such as taking strike and dip using a Brunton compass. The third day trip location was overnight, and in an even further location than the second. This trip again used new techniques such as using a Jacob’s Staff, but indoor accommodations were provided when not in the field. Finally, on the fourth trip, students returned back to the same location as the third for another overnight trip, solidifying the same techniques learned throughout the class. This time, students camped at the location.

This thesis aims to investigate the question, “*How does self-efficacy, identity, and sense of belonging change over the course of a geologic field techniques class?*” By measuring these factors, the effectiveness of the GEOL 380 course layout can be evaluated and potential improvements may be suggested.

Research Rationale

Despite the value that field-based coursework offers, some students still choose to not participate or are hesitant to join. Studies have been performed highlighting several reasons why a student may not participate (e.g., Jones and Washko, 2021; Peasland et al., 2021), but this study focuses on how a student’s outlook changes from beginning to end of the course. The aim of this study is to investigate factors which influence a student’s self-efficacy, identity, and sense of belonging, and to suggest interventions to improve these factors.

For the purposes of this study, we define “self-efficacy” as a student’s belief in their own capacity to complete geological tasks. “Identity” relates to how the student affiliates with the idea of being a geologist and/or scientist. A student’s “sense of belonging” is the degree to which they feel like they fit in with other geologists in the field. These three factors are important influences on geologic fieldwork because they are all indicators of the course’s effectiveness on the student’s development as a geoscience professional. Self-efficacy, identity, and sense of belonging should improve over the course of a fieldwork class.

The results of this study may lead to improvements in future renditions of the GEOL 380 class, by suggesting interventions to the instructor to apply for the next group. For instance, if the use of outdoor equipment such as tents or sleeping bags is identified as worrisome for students and this attitude did not change over the course, we can suggest spending more time in the classroom going over how to use equipment. Furthermore, other classes that include field components may be able to use the results of this study to mitigate the effects of barriers students may face, which may cause hesitation or disinterest. Instructors to courses such as field camp, oceanography, or earth history, which all include at least one obligatory field trip, can utilize the results of this research to better their course plans. This will ensure instructors are using time efficiently to focus on components that, if not properly addressed, may halter student academic performance.

Methods and Procedures

The sample population for this study were students taking GEOL 380 at CSUF in Spring 2023. This population was selected in an effort to improve future renditions of the course, which focuses on how to conduct geological fieldwork. This research was part of an ongoing study which will take place over subsequent years, in order to improve student satisfaction and course effectiveness.

After obtaining approval from the CSUF Institutional Review Board (IRB: HSR-22-23-193), online surveys (Appendix A) and Zoom interviews (Appendix B) were conducted during the first and last two weeks of the course. Prior to the start of the course, researchers collaborated with course instructors to determine which topics would be covered in class. Surveys were administered to students using the online Qualtrics platform, and asked questions pertaining to the students' identity as a geologist, levels of comfort and preparedness for field activities, how they feel towards field activities, and perceived competence in class skills taught in GEOL 380. Students were asked to respond to these questions based on a Likert scale, responding based on how well they identify with what was asked. In order to reduce response bias, reverse coded questions were included into the questionnaire. Some statements which students were asked to rank their agreement to included:

- *I feel "at home" in the Department of Geological Sciences.*
- *My family sees me as a scientist.*
- *How excited are you about interacting with classmates outside of the classroom?*

Interviews were conducted individually over Zoom with Dr. Virginia Isava and recorded for audio transcription. Participants were asked about their concerns and excitement related to the course, as well as feedback for the course in the post-course version of the interview.

Questions asked of interview participants included:

- *What do you worry about going wrong in the field?*
- *What was your prior experience outdoors?*
- *How do you feel about sharing your concerns with your instructors?*

In addition to the same questions asked at the start of the class, questions were asked during the end-of-course interview about the outcomes of the class, including:

- *What do you think should be changed?*
- *What do you think should stay the same?*
- *What turned out to be less of a problem than you originally expected?*
- *What turned out to be a bigger problem than you originally expected?*

Following the completion of the course, data collected through interviews and surveys were anonymized to remove subject identifiability. Names were redacted from responses and interviewees were assigned letters to distinguish pre and post course feedback.

Qualitative Analysis

Each anonymous interview audio file was then transcribed using Canvas Studio transcription software to form a time stamped audio file. To reduce errors and clearly identify the response to each question, software produced transcripts were individually reviewed alongside the audio file and updated for accuracy.

Responses for the 16 questions were organized on a spreadsheet outlining each of the students' responses to every question, which simplifies comparing all student responses to a single question. Each response to a question was reviewed to extract possible themes the answer

was related to. Then, once each response was evaluated for themes, a code book (Appendix C) was created to identify the themes that occur multiple times throughout the responses. The code book contains a table for each of the 16 interview questions and establishes a short-hand identifier for response themes, an explanation of the code, and an in-text example of the code. Each appendix also contains the number of instances where the code appears per question and the percentage of responses that included that particular code (which was determined after establishing reliability between researchers).

A series of inter-rater reliability tests was conducted between Virginia Isava and Adrian Remigio. During each test, three pre-course and three post-course responses were randomly selected to undergo qualitative coding. Each researcher independently reviewed the same six responses at a time, and using the code book previously established, coded the responses. Once this was completed, each set of coded responses were combined into a single spreadsheet in order to compare the differences between each rater. Where there was dissimilarity in the codes, both researchers offered their justifications in order to either redact a code from the response, add a code to the response, update the code book explanation for clarity, or remove a code from the book.

Once researchers came to an agreement on how the six sample responses should be coded, two more similar inter-rater reliability tests were performed to further establish reliability. A total of three rounds were conducted.

After agreeing with response codes, the complete spreadsheet of interview responses were coded by a single researcher. Once all of the interviews had been coded, the number of instances and percentages in which a code was included within the pre-course surveys and post-course surveys were added to the code book. This allowed direct comparison between the pre-course and post-course responses to distinguish changes throughout the course. Questions only found in the post-course interviews were considered feedback based rather than for comparison of self-efficacy, identity, sense of belonging, preparedness, or comfort.

Quantitative Analysis

Once all participants had completed the survey, results were automatically generated by the Qualtrics software on a spreadsheet. The anonymized survey data was then separated by each of the nine questions, where the results of pre and post course surveys were compared. The figures outlined the frequency in which a response was selected by a participant and can be directly compared to show changes within the theme that pertains to the question. In addition to containing multiple choice options, questions 4, 7, and 8 contain an option to select “other” and justify with free response. The number of reported “other” responses were minimal, leaving researchers unable to qualitatively code. Questions 5 and 9 were free response only questions, and these responses were qualitatively coded but not included into the code book due to low instances of codes.

Through both qualitative and quantitative data analysis methods, connections, patterns, and themes were identified to form conclusions, allowing us to make suggestions for course improvement. In particular, we analyzed which outlooks and perspectives related to the students’ identity as a geological scientist, sense of belonging within geological fieldwork, and self-efficacy with regards to geological coursework changed over the course of the class, and which remained the same. The preparedness and comfort of the student were also taken into consideration, as these factors affect a student’s experience in the field. These conclusions were

used to suggest changes to subsequent GEOL 380 courses, and potentially other scientific courses which include a fieldwork component.

Results

Self Efficacy

Students showed improvement in self efficacy after completion of the course in nearly all instructor provided learning aims (Fig. 2). Of the thirteen questioned competencies (Appendix A.1), students had the most trouble with explaining mineral formation; there was no improvement in positive response. The most improved task from the class was writing a regional geologic report summarizing field observations and interpretations. After completing the course, 50% of students (n=8) reported self-efficacy in writing these reports. Identification of a rock hand sample is also among the most improved, with six more students demonstrating self efficacy in this task. Five of the course targets (i.e., producing, interpreting, and explaining a geologic cross section; developing a geologic hypothesis; collect, test, and analyze field observations; and summarizing results) have improved to 100% (n=16) of students responding positively.

Identity as a Scientist

After completing the course, students expressed the most positive feelings towards their peers seeing them as a scientist. 44% more students (n=14) felt like their peers saw them as scientists, improving from a 38% positive response rate (n=6) (Fig. 3). No students started the class feeling unwelcomed within the science community at CSUF, which remained the same throughout the class. While no participants initially felt like they themselves weren't scientists, three responded neither agree nor disagree (80% positive response rate, n=13). After the course, students improved their scientist identity with 100% positive response (n=16) (8 responding somewhat agree and 8 responding strongly agree in the post-course survey).

Sense of Belonging

Sense of belonging amongst students did not improve throughout the class. In all survey questions regarding sense of belonging (Appendix A.2), less students responded positively following completion when compared with pre-course data. Responses to survey question 2 "Other students in the Department of Geological Sciences show me respect" has provided the most significant change in sense of belonging, with 20% less students (n=3) responding positively (Fig. 4). Feeling understood, welcomed, at home, and respected by staff, are also among the factors of sense of belonging which have decreased, with at least two fewer students responding positively in each category.

Levels of comfort

A. Working with others

When students were asked about how they felt working in groups in the field, generally the reaction was positive. Respondents mentioned that group work was beneficial to their understanding, allowed them to meet new peers, and promoted the continuation of existing friendships, which showed nominal change throughout the course. During post-course surveys, four students mentioned specific positive group work experiences and two students mentioned negative group work experiences from the class. Students also didn't mind traveling with their

peers for long stretches of time, eight stating that trips are great ways to build relationships and seven stating that they were not worried with no further elaboration during pre-course interviews. Post-course did not reveal any significant changes in group travel, other than two students mentioning they would prefer to drive themselves for various reasons.

The majority of students felt comfortable voicing their concerns with field instructors, 88% during the pre-test (n=14) and 80% in the post-test (n=12). While not mentioned during the beginning of the course, afterwards, it was revealed that 20% of students (n=3) had reservations about sharing concerns with field instructors because they did not want to cause further problems (Appendix C.9).

B. Working in the field

When asked about how they feel being outdoors for approximately eight hours in a day, 56% of respondents (n=9) in the beginning of the class stated that they enjoyed being outdoors for that long. Towards the end of the course, the number of students who enjoyed their time outdoors dropped to 40% (n=6). After the class, more students were aware about how weather can affect their experience in the field and while camping. Commonly mentioned was the concern for sun exposure during prolonged periods, 40% of students (n=6) considered weather following the course, which increased from 13% prior (n=2) (Appendix C.6). Furthermore, the course emphasized the importance of proper nutrition in the field. One student mentioned nutrition during pre-course interviews when asked about working in the field, which increased to four students during post-course. Only two students responded that they felt challenged working outdoors for extended periods prior to field trips, which remained the same throughout the class.

Most students (10 in both pre and post) provided a generally positive response when asked about how they felt sleeping outdoors. Two students mentioned past negative experiences which caused reservations about sleeping outdoors. Past negative experiences were not mentioned again during post interviews.

Preparedness for the Field

A. Prior Experiences

The majority of students had prior outdoor experiences; 11 students during the pre and post tests mentioned multiple experiences with outdoor recreational activities like camping or hiking. Only one student mentioned having limited experience when asked if they had been camping before. Students were also asked to elaborate on the facilities available to them. In the pre-course survey, 19% (n=3) of the students have only been camping with an RV, 63% (n=10) have been camping with bathroom access, 25% (n=4) without bathroom access, 25% (n=4) with showers, 56% (n=9) without access to showers, 13% (n=2) with kitchens, and 50% (n=8) without kitchens (Appendix C.12). During the post-course survey, 13% (n=2) of students mentioned their RV experience again, 67% (n=10) with bathrooms, 27% (n=4) without bathrooms, 47% (n=7) with showers, 40% (n=6) without showers, 20% (n=3) with kitchens, and 60% (n=9) without kitchens.

B. Resources

Respondents were asked what they were worried would not be considered by field instructors. 75% of students (n=12) felt confident in the amount of preparation the instructors had done for the course field trips during pre-course interviews (Appendix C.8). Following completion of the course, the number of students who felt confident in their instructors dropped to 53% (n=8). 13% of students (n=2) mentioned the student/instructor collaboration to create a “master doc” as beneficial to their experience, dropping down to 7% (n=1) afterwards. The

“master doc” was a student/instructor collaboration, created as a resource to ensure students knew how to properly prepare for the field. Included in this document were gear packing lists and additional resources where students could obtain additional gear. One respondent mentioned their concern about physical ability during the pre-course survey, increasing to two in the post-course. Health was an initial concern for one respondent which remained the same post-course. At the end of the course, 27% of the class (n=4) expressed concerns that the instructor did not consider student knowledge (ability to understand course tasks based on prior knowledge) which increased from the initial 6% (n=1).

Students were also asked about the resources and support they are aware of to support their fieldwork, and what additional resources they would like the department or university provide (Appendix C.10). The “master doc” was mentioned by 31% (n=5) of students during the pre-course, which dropped to 13% (n=2) during post-course. 19% of students (n=3) mentioned that they felt confident in the instructor's preparation which was not mentioned again during post-course (0%). Two students mentioned that they felt equipped for fieldwork given the amount of personal equipment they owned, which was also not mentioned again afterwards. Students found value in referring to faculty and staff as a resource, increasing to 47% (n=7) from 19% (n=3). Prior to the trips, 38% of students (n=6) were aware of/used camping equipment provided by the university or geological sciences department. When asked again following the field trips, 47% of students (n=7) were aware of/used the university or department provided camping gear. The request for additional health and food resources were mentioned by one respondent in each category, which remained the same throughout the course. 63% of students (n=63) during the pre-course interview vaguely mentioned that there were resources available to them, but did not specify. Afterwards, only 40% of respondents (n=6) mentioned these non-specific resources.

Course Prospects

A. Excitement

Pre-course surveys revealed that the majority of students were generally excited about what they would be doing in the class. There was a 100% (n=16) positive response rate in relation to excitement about camping, learning outdoors, exploring new places, and learning practical field skills. Aspects such as interacting with faculty outside the classroom, interacting with classmates outside the classroom, stepping out of their comfort zone, and applying classroom skills to the field had 88% (n=14), 94% (n=15), 88% (n=14), and 94% (n=15) positive response rates in the pre-course, respectively. Post-course surveys revealed the most negative change in interacting with classmates outside of the classroom, with three less students responding positively. Camping also had less excitement in the end, with two students feeling indifferent about the task and the rest being very excited. Applying what they learned in the field had an additional student respond positively, increasing from a 94% (n=15) positive response to 100% (n=16). Stepping outside of their comfort zone improved from an 88% (n=14) positive response rate to 94% (n=15), but two less students responded “very excited” and three more responded a little excited. Learning outdoors, interacting with faculty outside the classroom, exploring new places, and learning practical field skills did not show any change in regards to positive response, but learning outdoors and exploring new places improved to 100% of students (n=16) responding with the most positive response “very excited”. Interacting with faculty outside the classroom maintained the same amount of students responding negatively and

indifferent, but an additional student responded “very excited”. Learning practical skills, while maintaining 100% positive response (n=16), had an additional student respond most positively.

In addition to rating how excited the student was about specific aspects of the course, students were also asked to choose the top three factors they were most interested in (Appendix A.8). Of the eight options, the top three most selected responses were exploring new places (9 pre-course and 10 post-course), learning practical field skills (10 in pre-course and 8 in post-course), and applying classroom skills in the field (8 pre-course and 9 post-course). The least selected were interacting with classmates outside the classroom (5 pre-course and 4 post-course), stepping outside of your comfort zone (3 pre-course and 3 post-course), and interacting with faculty outside the classroom (2 pre-course and 3 post-course). When comparing pre-course and post-course, no significant changes between data sets are revealed. If showing any difference between the amount of pre- and post- course selections, differences were only by a factor of one student, with the exception of camping, having two additional selections in post course.

B. Worries

For worry, positive responses in student survey data are expressed by the two responses “not worried at all” and “not very worried”. Falling behind on other courses and missing other non- family, work, or school obligations were factors whose worry increased after completion of the course with four fewer students responding positively in each category. Prior to the field trips, 10 students responded positively about their worry in falling behind with other courses, but this decreased to six students in post-course. Levels of academic preparedness, physically being able to keep up with the group, the course workload, and knowledge not being useful in a future career decreased in positive response by three students each. The most improved initial worries were levels of preparedness for outdoor components, being overwhelmed by the situation, packing the right type/amount of food, obtaining field gear, and dealing with bodily functions (restroom, periods, etc.) in the field, each having an additional two positive responses. Factors that did not show any change from initial worry include being able to intellectually keep up with the group and missing work.

Students also ranked their top three worries in the course. The three most worrisome aspects of the course were keeping up with the group intellectually (six pre-course and seven post-course), levels of academic preparedness for course content (five pre-course and seven post-course), and the courses workload (four pre-course and four post-course). Worries about level of preparedness for the outdoor component of the class, sleeping outdoors, and sharing a tent with other students only appeared in pre-course surveys, with two selections on each factor. Skills not being useful for a future career, obtaining appropriate field gear, and working in groups in the field were worries that were revealed only in post-course, with two, three, and two selections, respectively. Factors which improved the most (less respondents in post-course than pre-course) were dealing with bodily functions (restroom, periods, etc.) (three pre-course and one post-course), other responsibilities (not family, work, or school) (three pre-course and one post-course), missing work (four pre-course and one post-course), and packing the right type/amount of food (four pre-course and one post-course). Factors which got worse were acquired knowledge not being useful to future careers (one pre-course and three post-course) and being overwhelmed by the situation (one pre-course and five post-course). Physical safety in the field and interacting with classmates/instructors outside of the classroom were not selected by any of the respondents as top worries in either the pre- or post- course surveys.

C. Post-Course Feedback

Students were asked a series of questions during the post-course survey pertaining to course structure (Appendix C.13-C.16). Responses revealed that 53% of the students (n=8) would like to see clearer instruction as to what is expected of them in the field, such as further guidance on what to do and what to complete when performing fieldwork. 27% of students (n=4) wanted more experience in specific subjects of the class (Appendix C.13), 20% mentioning that the labs assigned during lecture were beneficial to their understanding (Appendix C.14). 27% of students (n=4) also mentioned that they would prefer changing the timing of class meetings and field trips (Appendix C.13), but the majority of students (53%, n=8) mentioned the course structure (including scheduling and materials) were a positive aspect of the course (Appendix C.14). 13% of students (n=2) would like to see more variety in field trip locations (Appendix C.13), while 60% of students (n=9) enjoyed the structure of the field trips and would like them to remain the same (Appendix C.14).

60% of students (n=9) found that course materials were not as difficult to complete as expected (Appendix C.15), yet 60% of students (n=9) also mentioned that they had a hard time in the class related to a specific class subject (Appendix C.16). Time management was brought up 13% of the time (n=2) (Appendix C.16), mentioning either the timing of tips as a much larger or much smaller problem than originally anticipated. 20% of students found that camping was less worrisome than expected (n=3).

Discussion

Knowledge

The main benefit of integrating fieldwork into courses is to supplement knowledge of classroom taught techniques and skills by engaging in real world scenarios. This active and experimental engagement promotes higher order thinking and skill development (Jones and Washko, 2021). Self-efficacy improved amongst students, as several of the instructor outlined course competencies had 100% responding “somewhat well” or “very well”, which no competencies were prior. This outcome initially seems to conflict with evidence suggesting that knowledge was a pressing issue for students. 53% of students mentioned that they were most worried about their knowledge throughout the course during post-course interviews, and the majority of students found that course subjects were a larger problem than expected.

This discordance between overall self-efficacy and application of knowledge in the course shows the development of declarative knowledge, yet the lack of reinforcement of procedural knowledge. Declarative knowledge is related to knowing concepts and ideas (who, what, when, and where), while procedural knowledge is related to knowing the process or having the skill (how) (Ambrose et al., 2010). When thinking of driving a manual transmission car, declarative knowledge is knowing that in order to drive that car you would have to shift the gears, procedural knowledge is knowing how to shift the transmission and actually drive. 60% of students found that course materials like labs were not as difficult as expected, but students still felt that their preparedness for the academic content was lacking. Keeping up with the group intellectually was most frequently chosen as a worrisome aspect of the course, with a student stating in post-tests, “applying things that we learned in the classroom to the field could be a bit hard.”

With the minority of students participating in fieldwork prior to this course, the overall increase in feeling overwhelmed by the entire situation (being outdoors, social, etc.) may have been exacerbated by the feeling of lacking proper knowledge. Concerns about knowledge were

mostly directed towards tasks assigned in the field, rather than lecture assignments and lab. Course instructors did include tasks throughout the semester to reinforce procedural knowledge such as measuring strikes and dips of sample rocks and mapping locations on campus. However, students felt like they didn't possess the required procedural knowledge to complete field assignments, with 53% of students wishing that they had more guidance and clearer instructions on what to do/to complete in the field. One student summarized this feeling by describing themselves as, "very lost and sometimes ... just left to [their] own devices."

Additional benefits to fieldwork mentioned include co-production of knowledge and feedback between students and instructors (Jones and Washko, 2021). For assignments that were not assigned as part of the field trips, such as test locations around campus, students were able to work closely with all of their classmates and both instructors (the professor and assistant). When out in the field, students worked in much smaller groups and didn't have access to help from instructors as readily as needed, given the expansive area assigned to be covered during the field trips. Faculty were one of the most mentioned resources when reflecting on the class. This suggests that access to instructor help was an issue in the field, and students were not ready for the jump in scale that the field trips involved.

Being Outdoors

This course solidified the excitement towards learning in alternative environments, with 60% of students reporting excitement in post tests. Field trips deepened the understanding of classroom taught concepts by applying them to the "real world" – one student mentioned they were excited for, "using the techniques that are taught in the class actually in a real world setting, rather than just like a classroom setting." The initial excitement of students towards what they are learning builds intrinsic motivation, setting the foundation for further knowledge building and higher order thinking (Behrendt & Franklin, 2014).

Prior experience in general did not seem to have a discernible positive or negative effect, therefore, a student's prior experience did not necessarily play a factor in a student's success in a fieldwork course. The majority of students in the study had prior experience with the outdoors, as only 19% mentioned limited involvement during the pre-course interviews. Prior experiences with the outdoors included being in scouts as a child and working outdoors in the military, but the most mentioned outdoor experiences were recreational in nature such as hiking and backpacking (69% of students). Further reinforcing the overall predisposed enjoyment of the outdoors, when asked about being outdoors for around eight hours a day, 25% of students gave a general positive reaction and 56% of students expressed enjoyment, saying things like, "I'm excited for it. Actually, I like being outdoors, so it's going to be fun for me."

The lack of correlation between experience of outdoor fieldwork and extracurricular recreational activities suggests why prior experience doesn't instinctively lead to success in a fieldwork course. After completing all field trips, positive reactions towards spending eight hours a day outdoors dropped from 81% to 60% (generally positive and enjoyment responses). Eight hours of fieldwork, performing complex tasks and trying to solve problems in sometimes the least accommodating environments, is not the same as spending the same amount of time on a leisurely hike or in a campground. This contrast may not have been apparent enough to the students prior to this course, as only 19% of students mentioned having been on class field trips before. More students were concerned with the weather, bringing the right gear, and physically keeping up with the rest of the group after the course than prior. This potentially demotivated the students, as initial excitement for being outdoors diminished throughout the course.

Study Limitations

A major limitation to this research is the small sample size. With around 16 respondents, even changes among one or two students' reported responses had large impacts on result percentages. While we were able to form suggestions to future renditions of this course, the small sample size may not be representative of students in future renditions of this class, as well as other courses at different universities. Further research on future classes, given the outcomes of this course, will increase the number of samples tested and therefore conclusions will be more precise.

Each interview section should have only included a single question for the student to respond to. In this research, interview questions 10 and 12 (Appendix B.10 & B. 12) had multiple parts of the question asked. All respondents interpreted questions differently, but there were instances where one, part, or all of the questions were addressed, making it difficult to compare pre- and post-.

Another limitation was that one researcher, Adrian, was a student in this course alongside respondents. Adrian's data was not included in the research and interview/survey responses were anonymized to mitigate bias and identifiability. While measures were done to prevent bias, it was difficult to not stress personal experiences in the class (i.e., inflating issues in the course with those that Adrian personally struggled with).

Suggestions for Future Courses

Instructors for this course aimed to improve student knowledge on thirteen factors, including: producing and interpreting a geological cross section; identifying and explaining formation of mineral and rock samples; developing a geological hypothesis; collect, test, and analyze geologic field observations to form geologic results; and be able to explain your results to a non-geologist peer (Appendix A.1). In all aspects, except for explaining the likely processes that formed a mineral, students responded with a positive change in self efficacy, with as many as eight students improving in multiple aspects. Factors relating to self efficacy that improved the most were producing a geological cross section and using field observations to interpret geological history. Improvement in these subjects are expected as in the field, most of the time was spent distinguishing rock units and measuring strikes and dips to create a geological map. These geological maps helped students write reports on the area's geological history. Interpreting a cross section, identifying a mineral hand sample, explaining rock formation processes, and developing a geologic hypothesis were factors which students had the least positive change in. While students spent a majority of field time creating a geological cross section, interpreting a geological cross section showed little positive change as not enough class time was spent on how to read and interpret cross sections. Examples of cross sections given to the students were complicated and hard to understand with much more detail compared to the cross sections that students created. Little to no class time was spent focusing on minerals, their identification or formation. Being a mid-level geology course, the student population varied in their educational journey as some students had taken higher level mineralogy courses while it was some others' first semester at CSUF after transferring from community college. This likely also explains why there was no positive change in explaining mineral formation. The class covered a variety of geological settings including coastal and desert environments. Not enough class time was spent going over how rocks in different settings formed based on the low positive change. While instructors briefly went over rock units before setting students free in the field, this was not

enough time for students to properly digest and interpret rock formation processes. Most students had never been to the field trip locations either, and did not know what to expect beforehand. This made it hard to develop a geologic hypothesis as students only saw the location pictures the day before the trip. More time needs to be spent exploring locations before physically visiting sites by utilizing tools such as Google Earth to form a base knowledge. In the field, more time should also be spent allowing the students to explore and make initial observations before assigning tasks.

In general, students felt less sense of belonging after completing the course. In the survey, all responses showed a negative change except for two reverse-coded questions which were put in place to ensure surveyee thoroughness (the data is consistently showing a negative change despite some increases in positive response due to the question). Students may have felt less respected by peers in the Department of Geological Sciences at the end of the semester compared to the beginning because of tensions between students on track to earn a Bachelor's of Arts versus a Bachelors of Science degree. Both degree types have varying required courses, but students are free to take classes within the department like GEOL 380. Because of this, there were different amounts of knowledge from prior classes that may have helped some students and made others feel left out. Class time, especially during the first few meetings, should be spent establishing the knowledge base of that semester's class. Class knowledge will differ from person to person, and from semester to semester. This may also be why more students felt less respect from students in the other degree type. As a department, students felt less welcomed, less "at home", less like they are understood and less like they belong within the geological sciences. This could be because students felt left behind not understanding coursework while others and instructors in the class kept going. The entire class should ensure everyone is able to keep up and students should feel comfortable opening up about needing help as students feel less respected by faculty and staff in the department. While about half of the students consistently mentioned group collaboration as helpful to understanding concepts in the field, less students mentioned that they were open to sharing concerns with instructors and still had reservations about reaching out to instructors for help after completing the class. Early meetings should be spent establishing rapport among students and instructors, especially since so much time will be spent together during trips. The very first meeting of this course was through virtual modalities due to an emergency affecting campus, which may have affected the ability to establish relationships early on. Also, the class should have regularly scheduled meetings more frequently than once a week. Because this class was once a week on a Friday (many students don't come to campus on Fridays), class meetings exceeded student attention spans and many students could go two weeks without interacting with the curriculum if they missed a class. More time can be spent focusing on course topics that didn't improve as much as expected and preparing for field trips by meeting twice a week. In addition, students will be more engaged by shorter session times.

In addition to feeling like students belong within the department, another aim of the course is to improve students' identity of being a scientist. After completing the course, the most improved aspect of identity is the perception of peers seeing the student as a scientist. This is most likely because of the strong collaboration aspect of the class, explaining the improvements in the self identity as a scientist. As students got to know each other, there was an increase in some students feeling like they don't have much in common with other students in their science classes. There was little to no change in perception of family viewing the student as a scientist, feeling welcoming in the science community at the university, and being a scientist as a big part of who they are. The only negative change relating to a student's identity was feeling like they

belonged in a science field at CSUF. This could be because the student felt lost on assignments and didn't know what to do, which is why time should be spent making students feel welcomed to bolster their success in the department.

Students in this class had varying levels of experience in the outdoors, from only going out during class field trips to those who worked outdoors in the military. In addition to being outdoors, there are various levels of camping experience, most having experience with limited utilities. After being asked about how they felt about sleeping outdoors before and after their experience in the class, there was no improvement in concern for bringing the right gear or enough of it and a negative change on bringing enough food and water. More time should be spent focusing on bringing the right gear and enough of it based on the environmental conditions of the location. Furthermore, if there is room, extra supplies like water and sunscreen should be kept in the vehicles and be accessible in case a student forgot anything they need to be successful in the field. Fewer students mentioned that they enjoyed being outdoors for about eight hours a day after being in the field. Students were initially not concerned with the weather, but mentioned after that the weather and sun exposure negatively affected their experience. Weather should be checked several times leading up to the trip and it should be stressed to students to bring multiple layers of clothing because weather conditions can change fast. While there was no improvement in those mentioning they had no concerns about anything going wrong in the field, the class did ease student concerns about extreme situations and weather, as no students mentioned these in the post course interview. Concerns about knowledge in the field to complete assignments did increase as students felt lost on assigned tasks. Responding when asked what aspects of the course should be changed in the post course interview, the majority of students mentioned that they would like to see clearer instructions as to what is expected of them in the field. Students were handed an assignment at the beginning of the trip to do tasks they had never done before. Most of the time, students did not complete the assignments and were required to complete it before arriving back on campus. It should be stressed which tasks within the assignment are the most important, what is due, when it is due, and how long each section should take them. Also, being able to view the assignment a couple of days beforehand would allow students to prepare for what is asked of them.

Preparedness in several aspects (knowledge, outdoors, relationships, etc.) was evaluated at the beginning and end of the course to investigate whether prior experiences affected class outcomes. Towards the beginning of the course, most students felt confident in the amount of preparation the instructors have done but a negative change in responses showed that initial perceptions of instructor preparedness did not hold up. Initial impressions may have been based on the creation of a master document that included packing lists and tips for the field trips, which was mentioned in both pre and post course interviews. Less students mentioned the resources available to them at the end of the course. This could simply be because they were initially introduced to resources like the store REI or the department office at the beginning and did not utilize any resources during the course. This also could be a negative response because the provided resource locations were unable to provide the student with gear they needed. They had just been recently introduced to the resources (recency bias) so it was fresh, they also didn't know what they were missing until out in the field.

At the end of the course, students were asked what aspects of the course should change, stay the same, was a larger problem than expected, and was a smaller problem than expected. Other than the majority of students mentioning issues with knowledge on assignments, some students mentioned specific subjects they would like more experience on and to take field trips in

more of a variety of locations. The mentioning of specific class subjects students needed more clarification on pinpoints what should be more heavily covered in future renditions of this course. Many students were initially concerned about their time management and how the course and trips would fit into their schedule, but this turned out to be less of a problem than expected which is most likely why the majority of respondents mentioned the course structure i.e., scheduling, material, etc. as a positive aspect of the course that should stay the same.

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Figures/Tables

Figure 1: The benefits of fieldwork, highlighting transferable skills alongside geological techniques pertaining to coursework.

Figure 2: Changes in self-efficacy between pre- and post-course assessments. Abilities for nearly all intended learning goals improved as a result of this course. Aspects which improved the most include producing a geological cross-section, explaining a geological cross-section, and creating a report on geologic observations/interpretations.

Figure 3: Changes between student science identity between pre- and post- course. Student perception of their peers seeing themselves as a scientist was the most improved, with 7 more students responding positively in post-course surveys than the pre-course. Feeling like they belong in the sciences at CSUF showed the least improvement, with one less student responding positively.

Figure 4: Changes in positive response regarding sense of belonging between Pre- and Post-course surveys. The perception of respect from other geology students decreased the most in positive response, with 3 less students mentioning responding positively. Students also felt like their degree type was less respected by other students in the geological sciences department.

Figure 3: Changes in preparedness between pre and post course surveys. Towards the end of the course, less students were worried about extreme situations and weather but more students were worried about knowledge and bringing the correct gear.

Figure 4: Pre- and Post- course assessment of instructor/student relations. Less students felt open to sharing concerns with their field instructors after completing the course, with more students feeling like they would rather keep issues to themselves.

Appedicies

Appendix A: Qualtrics Survey

A.1: How well can you?

	Not well at all (1)	Not very well (2)	Somewhat well (3)	Very well (4)
Produce a geological cross-section (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interpret a geological cross-section (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Identify a mineral hand sample (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Identify a rock hand sample (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Explain the likely process(es) that formed a mineral (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Explain the likely process(es) that formed a rock (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Develop a geologic hypothesis (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collect, test, and analyze geologic field observations (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Summarize geologic results (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Explain what a geological cross-section is to a non-geologist friend (10)

Use your field observations of a region to explain its geological history to a non-geologist friend (11)

Write a geologic report summarizing your observations and interpretations of a region (12)

Give a presentation on a geological concept in a way that's accessible to non-geologists (13)

A.2: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
I am understood as a person by the people at the Department of Geological	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Sciences
(1)

I feel
connected
to the
university
faculty and
staff in the
Department
of
Geological
Sciences
(2)

I have
found the
Department
of
Geological
Sciences to
be
welcoming
(3)

Other
students in
the
Department
of
Geological
Sciences
show me
respect (4)

Students
earning my
degree type
(either B.A.
or B.S.) are
not
respected
by other
students in
the
Department
of
Geological
Sciences
(5)

Members of faculty and staff in the Department of Geological Sciences show respect toward me (6)

Students earning my degree type (either B.A. or B.S.) are respected by members of faculty and staff in the Department of Geological Sciences (7)

I do not matter to others in the Geological Sciences department (8)

I feel "at home" in the Department of Geological Sciences (9)

I feel like I belong in the Department of Geological Sciences (10)

A.3: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
I am a scientist (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel like I belong in a science field at this university (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Being a scientist is a big part of who I am (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel welcomed in the science community at this university (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I do not have much in common with the other students in my science classes (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

My family sees me as a scientist (6)	<input type="radio"/>				
My peers see me as a scientist (7)	<input type="radio"/>				

A.4: How excited are you about:

	Not excited at all (1)	Not very excited (2)	Neither excited nor not excited (3)	A little excited (4)	Very excited (5)
Camping (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Learning outdoors (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interacting with faculty outside of the classroom (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interacting with classmates outside of the classroom (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Exploring new places (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Stepping outside of your comfort zone (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Applying what you've learned in the classroom to the field (7)

Learning practical field skills (ex. how to use a compass, how to make/read a map) (8)

Other: (9)

A.6: Select the top three things that you are most excited about:

- Camping (1)
- Learning outdoors (2)
- Interacting with faculty outside of the classroom (3)
- Interacting with classmates outside of the classroom (4)
- Exploring new places (5)
- Stepping outside of your comfort zone (6)
- Applying what you've learned in the classroom to the field (7)
- Learning practical field skills (ex. how to use a compass, how to make/read a map) (8)

Other: (9) _____

A.5: If you feel comfortable, please explain why these things excite you the most:

A.7: How worried are you about:

	Not worried at all (1)	Not very worried (2)	Neither worried nor not worried (3)	A little worried (4)	Very worried (5)
Your level of preparedness for the academic content of this course (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Your level of preparedness for the outdoor component of this course (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Using scientific equipment (ex. compasses, maps) in the field (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Being able to keep up with the group (physically) (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Being able to keep up with the group (intellectually) (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

This course's workload (6)	<input type="radio"/>				
Falling behind on other courses because of this course's field trips (7)	<input type="radio"/>				
Missing work to attend field trips (8)	<input type="radio"/>				
Missing family obligations to attend field trips (9)	<input type="radio"/>				
Missing other responsibilities/obligations (ex. religious holidays, extracurricular activities, dentist appointments) to attend field trips (10)	<input type="radio"/>				
Being overwhelmed by the situation (ex. sensory overload) (11)	<input type="radio"/>				
Working in groups in the field (12)	<input type="radio"/>				
Packing the right amount/type of food (13)	<input type="radio"/>				
Buying/obtaining appropriate field gear (14)	<input type="radio"/>				
Sleeping outdoors (15)	<input type="radio"/>				
Sharing a tent with another student (16)	<input type="radio"/>				

Dealing with bodily functions (bathroom breaks, periods, etc.) in the field (17)	<input type="radio"/>				
Physical safety in the field (18)	<input type="radio"/>				
Interacting with other students outside of the classroom (19)	<input type="radio"/>				
Interacting with instructors outside of the classroom (20)	<input type="radio"/>				
Feeling left out during field trips (21)	<input type="radio"/>				
The knowledge you acquire in the field not being useful for your future career (22)	<input type="radio"/>				
The skills you acquire in the field not being useful for your future career (23)	<input type="radio"/>				
Other: (24)	<input type="radio"/>				

A.8: Select the top three things that you are most worried about:

- Your level of preparedness for the academic content of this course (1)
- Your level of preparedness for the outdoor component of this course (2)
- Using scientific equipment (ex. compasses, maps) in the field (3)
- Being able to keep up with the group (physically) (4)
- Being able to keep up with the group (intellectually) (5)

- This course's workload (6)
- Falling behind on other courses because of this course's field trips (7)
- Missing work to attend field trips (8)
- Missing family obligations to attend field trips (9)
- Missing other responsibilities/obligations (ex. religious holidays, extracurricular activities, dentist appointments) to attend field trips (10)
- Being overwhelmed by the situation (ex. sensory overload) (11)
- Working in groups in the field (12)
- Packing the right amount/type of food (13)
- Buying/obtaining appropriate field gear (14)
- Sleeping outdoors (15)
- Sharing a tent with another student (16)
- Dealing with bodily functions (bathroom breaks, periods, etc.) in the field (17)
- Physical safety in the field (18)
- Interacting with other students outside of the classroom (19)
- Interacting with instructors outside of the classroom (20)

- Feeling left out during field trips (21)
- The knowledge you acquire in the field not being useful for your future career (22)
- The skills you acquire in the field not being useful for your future career (23)
- Other: (24) _____

A.9: If you feel comfortable, please explain why these things worry you the most:

Appendix B: Interview Questions

- B.1:** What are/were you most excited about related to the field component of this course?
- B.2:** What are/ were you most worried about related to the field component of this course?
- B.3:** What are/were you worried about going wrong in the field?
- B.4:** How do you feel about working in groups in the field?
- B.5:** How do you feel about traveling with peers for long stretches of time?
- B.6:** How do you feel about being outdoors for ~8 hours in a day?
- B.7:** How do you feel about sleeping outdoors?
- B.8:** What were you worried would not be considered by the instructors who organized the field trip?
- B.9:** How do you feel about sharing your concerns with field instructors?

B.10: This next question has two parts to it. What resources and support are you aware of to help you prepare and equip for the field? What additional resources and support would you like to see the department and/or university provide?

B.11: What is your prior experience with the outdoors?

B.12: In general, have you been camping before? How long was the trip? Did you have access to bathrooms? Showers? Kitchens?

B.13: What aspects of this course do you think should be changed? (Only asked in post-course interview)

B.14: What aspects of this course do you think should stay the same? (Only asked in post-course interview)

B.15: What aspects of the course turned out to be less of a problem than you originally expected? (Only asked in post-course interview)

B.16: What aspects of the course turned out to be a bigger problem than you originally expected? (Only asked in post-course interview)

Appendix C: Code Book

Appendix C1						
Interview Q1: What are/were you most excited about related to the field component of this course?						
Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Career	2	13	0	0	Usefulness in future career plans, assists in preparing for future jobs.	" I think just learning and using the techniques that are used in this career field and getting to do the hands-on part of it"
S.C	1	6	0	0	Mentions specific career application. (subset of career)	"I'm hoping to get into paleontology fieldwork"
Field	2	13	0	0	Gaining experience in fieldwork/field techniques/skills	"having ... hands on experience where I'm actually in the field learning how to do things the way that geologists know how to do."
New	5	31	0	0	Excitement for learning subject that is new to them	"I've only taken two geology courses, so I'm still kind of new."

Outdoors	3	19	1	7	Desire to be outdoors	"And it gets me a good reason to go outdoors and learn about Earth."
L.E	3	19	6	40	Learning environment. Alternative learning environment to traditional classroom. Also includes applying knowledge/skills previously learned in the classroom in a new environment	"For me, I think it's the new environment of learning, because I've just been used to being stuck in the classroom or like somewhere on campus,"
Place	1	6	1	7	Seeing new places	"I'm looking forward to the most and getting to go on the field trips and getting to see some really interesting places"
Group	3	19	1	7	Desire to work in groups an/or interacting with peers	"being able to work with a group is really exciting and learning together when we're at the moment. "
Inst.	1	6	3	20	Learning how to use field instruments and equipment	"learn how to use different materials like a compass"

Appendix C2						
Interview Q2: What are/ were you most worried about related to the field component of this course?						
Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response

Class	1	6	1	7	Time management related to students' courseload on all classes. (subset of obligation)	"Probably losing time to do assignments since I take the whole weekend to do assignments for my classes"
Know	6	38	7	47	Being unable to fully understand course tasks based on prior knowledge. Being overwhelmed by course materials.	"I worry about keeping up intellectually because I'm a slow learner"
Obligation	4	25	0	0	Prior obligations that participation of this course may take away from.	"It's probably like if I have obligations on Saturdays, like field trips, I don't know if I could be able to make them sometimes, most of the time I can make it"
Phys.	1	6	3	20	Being unable to physically keep up with students and faculty in the field, i.e. physical stress/exhaustion.	"Honestly, just trying to keep up with like others. I feel like I might fall behind."
Gear	4	25	3	20	Not bringing the right gear to be out in the field, bringing insufficient supplies/food, or not knowing how to use gear.	"Maybe just like readiness and making sure. I was worried I wouldn't have everything I need at the time, because there is a lot to pack when you're going out on the field."
Weather	1	6	1	7	Concerns about how weather can affect the students experience out in the field or camping.	"just maybe sleeping outdoors, depending what the weather's like, if its cold."
Grade	0	0	1	7	Concerns about course grading/grade outcome.	"a real tough class, so I guess getting a good grade."

Appendix C3						
Interview Q3: What are/were you worried about going wrong in the field?						
Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
No	4	25	5	33	Does not have any concerns (no further elaboration).	"Nothing in particular, I feel like everything will be alright."
Injury	6	38	6	40	Concerns for bodily injury/illness of themselves or their peers.	"Nothing academically, I think just getting sick in some way."
E.S	3	19	0	0	Facing non-weather out of the ordinary situations such as animal attacks or natural disasters.	"Maybe a freak natural disaster, like an earthquake or something"
Weather	2	13	0	0	Concerns about how weather can affect the students experience out in the field or camping.	"Bad weather, thats always a bad thing."
Know	2	13	4	27	Being unable to fully understand course tasks based on prior knowledge, being overwhelmed by course materials.	"Being unprepared, possibly not having the knowledge of what I'm supposed to do when I'm in the field."
Lost	1	6	0	0	Lack of communication, not being able to find the group, being "stuck in the middle of nowhere".	"Following the topographic map was a bit tricky as well, pinpointing where you were at."
Gear	1	6	3	20	Not bringing the right gear to be out in the field, or bringing insufficient supplies.	"Running out of food, or water."

Appendix C4
Interview Q4: How do you feel about working in groups in the field?

Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Help	7	44	7	47	Group collaboration is seen as beneficial, adding to the students' understanding of the coursework.	"Along with the collaboration I think that working with people definitely helps, at least for me personally."
Harm	1	6	0	0	Describes downsides of groupwork	"if it's a group project type situation you never know who you're going to be grouped with and if they're going to be willing to pull their weight in whatever assignment or project it is."
Meet	4	25	1	7	Excitement to meet new peers and discuss topics with like-minded individuals.	"They have a lot of interests that coincide with my interests too, so there are a lot more fun to talk to. I'm actually just pretty excited to get to know more people that like what I like."
Ind	1	6	1	7	Prefers working individually.	"Generally speaking, I don't like working in groups because I don't like when my grade depends on somebody else"
N.E	0	0	2	13	Describes a past negative experience of group work.	"You never know who you're going to be grouped with and if they're going to be willing to pull their weight in whatever assignment or project it is."

Pos	0	0	4	27	Mentions a positive groupwork experience from this class.	"I'm a fan of it, especially if it's some people that I like. For instance, there was a group about four of us in the 380 class were kind of always in groups, in different field trips. We always stuck together. So we were like, so we were friends. So it kind of made it just more enjoyable."
Neg	0	0	2	13	Mentions a neg groupwork experience from this class.	"some of the first field trips were at the beginning of the semester and it's a little awkward working in groups at that point"
Friend	3	19	1	7	Has previous relationships with other students in the class	"I'm looking forward to is, especially because I've got some friends in the class."
Good	1	6	2	13	General positive reaction with no additional information.	"I'm fine with working with groups and like splitting up tasks, talking about tasks."

Appendix C5						
Interview Q5: How do you feel about traveling with peers for long stretches of time?						
Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Relations	8	50	8	53	Sees peer travel as a way to bond, create new relationships, and converse.	"I think it is a great way to bond and build strong, lasting relationships."
Anxious	1	6	1	7	Concerns about the social aspect of travel.	"Maybe a little bit of that social anxiety."
Solo	0	0	2	13	Prefers to/did drive themselves to class trips.	"I'm OK, I'm experienced with that, and I'm OK with it. If options are provided for me to drive myself, I definitely take that option."

N.W	6	38	3	20	Does not have any concerns (no further elaboration).	"I feel pretty confident about it. It's like a road trip."
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Appendix C6						
Interview Q6: How do you feel about being outdoors for ~8 hours in a day?						
Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Enjoy	10	63	6	40	Enjoys the time spent outdoors.	"I'm excited for it. Actually, I like being outdoors, so it's going to be fun for me."
Weather	0	0	3	20	Concerned about how weather can affect the students experience out in the field or camping.	"You got to be ready For a long day, depending on the weather too."
Sun	2	13	3	20	Concerned about being exposed to the sun for prolonged periods of time. (subset of weather)	"I think it'll be fine as long as I take breaks and I'm protected from sun."
Chall.	2	13	2	13	Concerned about, or felt challenged by, working outdoors for extended amounts of time. Things that would impede on their experience outdoors.	"Working outdoors for eight hours a day is challenging. Hanging out outdoors, doing whatever I want is really nice."
Nutr.	1	6	4		Concerned about/mindful of hydration and eating enough food given the conditions.	"I could do 13, 14, but, you know, it's just making sure that I have enough food, enough water as long as I'm prepared for the long day ahead."
Pos	3	19	3	20	General positive reaction (no further elaboration).	"I'm OK with that. Yeah."

Appendix C7						
Interview Q7: How do you feel about sleeping outdoors?						
Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Gear	5	31	4	27	Mindful of bringing enough of the right gear to be out in the field.	"It really depends on how well I prepare for it, but its usually OK as long as I get everything prepared"
N.P.E	1	6	0	0	Reservations about sleeping outdoors based on previous negative experiences.	"I mean, it's not my favorite, but I'm used to it, I guess."
P.P.E	0	0	3	20	Enjoys sleeping outdoors based on previous positive experiences.	"I love it. I'm a camper. I camp annually"
Neutral	4	25	5	33	No strong feelings (positive or negative) described, neutral or fine	I feel pretty good about that. Might not get as well as sleep, but it was still sleep, so."
Prep.	1	6	0	0	Feels prepared to be in the field.	"I'm fine with it, I've done it before"
E.S	1	6	1	7	Facing non-weather out of the ordinary situations such as animal attacks or natural disasters.	"As long as there's no bear working or like mountain lions."
Pos	10	63	10	67	General positive reaction.	"I'm totally comfortable sleeping outdoors."

Appendix C8						
Interview Q8: What were you worried would not be considered by the instructors who organized the field trip?						
Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response

Prep.	12	75	8	53	Feels confident in the amount of preparation the instructors have done for the course.	"I don't think I was worried too much about what the instructors organized or what they didn't consider. I felt like everything was pretty much very, very planned for."
Attend	1	6	0	0	Worried about having an alternative for those who are not able to attend the field trip, i.e., a virtual option.	"The big thing that I am thinking they might not have considered is if somebody can't go on a field trip. What is it able to be made up virtually somehow?"
M.D	2	13	1	7	Mentions the class master doc (provides list of supplies, food, etc.) as beneficial to their preparedness.	"I didn't really have any questions when they were brought up because it was all the information already presented to us. It's very accessible, very easy to understand."
Phys.	1	6	2	13	Being unable to physically keep up with students and faculty in the field.	"Just the fact that some people may not be able to physically handle being in the field as long."
Know	1	6	4	27	Being unable to fully understand course tasks based on prior knowledge, being overwhelmed by course materials.	"They didn't consider just not being able to manage with the different amount of times it takes each person to learn and understand the concept."

Health	1	6	1	7	Concern that the instructors would not consider students' personal health issues.	"I have iron problems, so sometimes I get really lightheaded and I might need a break... I dont want to slow down the group."
Obligation	1	6	0	0	Prior obligations that participation of this course may take away from.	"It's probably like if I have obligations on Saturdays, like field trips, I don't know if I could be able to make them sometimes, most of the time I can make it"

Appendix C9						
Interview Q9: How do you feel about sharing your concerns with field instructors?						
Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Open	14	88	12	80	Comfortable speaking to instructors about their concerns.	"I feel like I's be pretty open about it if I had a concern, I would probably just speak out, speak to them directly, if I had any real concerns."
Shy	2	13	1	7	Wary about voicing concerns to instructors because they feel nervous or shy.	"I'm just a shy person in general, but with teachers I am always nervous to ask questions."
Kept	0	0	3	20	Reservations about voicing concerns to instructors because of possible response, troubling the instructor, or creating further issues.	"I feel like I can share them but I'd rather just keep it to myself because I don't want to bring more problems to the table."

Advocate	1	6	0	0	Comfortable speaking to instructors about student's own concerns, and is also willing to advocate for other students who may not be as comfortable. (subset of open).	"I try to work with them or talk with them or even be the voice for other people if they're not comfortable talking with people."
Peers	1	6	2	13	Would rather voice their concerns to their peers first rather than going directly to the instructors	"I usually try to connect with my peers instead. See where they're at and then someone's brave enough to ask the professor."

Appendix C10						
Interview Q10: This next question has two parts to it. What resources and support are you aware of to help you prepare and equip for the field? What additional resources and support would you like to see the department and/or university provide?						
Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Skills	0	0	0	0	Wants to learn field-related skills.	"a resource that might be helpful is like a class on how to set up certain equipment, like certain camping items"
M.D	5	31	2	13	Provided list of items that will be needed for fieldwork.	"I know we're going to have a session before class, to go through a checklist of what we need before the field trip"
Food	1	6	1	7	Provided food, or money for food.	"money towards food on camping trips"

Geo G	2	13	2	13	Mentions specific geological gear to support their studies.	"I think it would be nice if the university would provide us with, like a sort of kit, I guess, for geology field stuff. Like a compass and magnifying glass and magnets and all the little tools that we use, HCL."
Camp G	6	38	7	47	Resources provided by either the university or the department for camping in the field.	"I'm aware that if you don't have a tent or a sleeping mat or any of equipment like that, you can just go to the department, ask, can I get a tent or can I get this and stuff like that?"
People	3	19	7	47	Mentions faculty/staff as a resource.	"Professor Metcalf laid it all out for us, everything we would be doing to a T. She had office hours for us. She responded very quickly to any questions. So she was like my number one resource. "
Prep	3	19	0	0	Feels confident in the amount of preparation the instructors have done for the course.	"I'm aware that Cal State Fullerton has resources that I can reach out to, and if I need help preparing or just buying equipment, they are one of the best people to go to if you don't know what to do."
Had	2	13	0	0	Feels that they are prepared for the field with personal equipment.	"I have a lot of the resources for camping already on my own, so I wasn't that concerned with finding new equipment."

Health	1	6	1	7	Concerned that the instructors would not consider their personal health issues.	"Maybe some more emotional support and mental support on trips...I get really bad anxiety."
Resources	10	63	6	40	Mentions that resources are available, but does not specify what those resources are (vague).	"I'm aware that the university, the department, you could go and ask."

Appendix C11						
Interview Q11: What is your prior experience with the outdoors?						
Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Prior	3	19	1	7	Mentions previous class field trips.	"I've been on field trips for geology like in mineralogy and hydrology, and I have had a great experience with them no issues at all."
Scouts	2	13	1	7	Mentions girl/boy/cub scouts as prior outdoor experience. (subset of growing up).	"Growing up I did cub scouts and everything, so I was very familiar with like being outdoors and camping and everything."
Rec.	11	69	11	73	Student has multiple experiences in the outdoors recreationally such as hiking or camping.	"Well, I'm a backpacker, so I like to go on backpacking trips quite often."
Little	3	19	1	7	Limited experience with the outdoors.	"Very little and mostly been hiking, but that's not even a lot I go like once every couple of years."

Grow	2	13	2	13	Multiple experiences outdoors growing up on vacations.	"Kind of grew up going to spending summer vacations in Arizona on the water."
Work	3	19	2	13	Experience outdoors due to work.	"I spent a few hours in the field when I was in the military and later in contracting"

Appendix C12						
Interview Q12: In general, have you been camping before? How long was the trip? Did you have access to bathrooms? Showers? Kitchens?						
Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Little	1	6	1	7	Limited/no experience with the outdoors.	"I've been camping, but I was like six so I don't remember that much."
RV	3	19	2	13	Experience with camping is limited to RV camping with full facilities.	"I've been camping, but I was like six so I don't remember that much."
BY	10	63	10	67	Has been camping before and did have access to bathrooms	"There was bathrooms that were bolted and there was no showers."
BN	4	25	4	27	Has been camping before but had no access to bathrooms	"The longest camping trip I went on with the boys was probably about five days, I think, and there were no bathrooms, no showers. And we brought our own kitchen. So no kitchen."
SY	4	25	7	47	Has been camping before and had access to showers	"That particular trip, I had access to shower and bathrooms but other trips I've had no shower but a pit toilet."

SN	9	56	6	40	Has been camping before but did not have access to a shower	"Spent you know, longest was probably about two weeks backpacking and of course, no, there was no showers or bathrooms or kitchens other than what we brought. "
KY	2	13	3	20	Has been camping before and did have access to a kitchen	"And yes, we did have access to bathrooms. We didn't have access to showers or and we had a little kitchen"
KN	8	50	9	60	Has been camping before but did not have access to a kitchen.	And actually, I don't think I've ever had kitchens. You just kind of bring your own kitchen equipment.

Appendix C13

Interview Q13: What aspects of this course do you think should be changed? (Only asked in post-course interview)

Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Locations	N/A	N/A	2	13	Would like to see more variety of field trip locations.	"Maybe a bigger variety of geologic settings like we did one trip to Vasquez rocks, a day trip I think, and then the whole rest of the semester has been Rainbow Basin."
Timing	N/A	N/A	4	27	Wants changes in the timing of the course, including class meetings and field trips.	"I mean, when it's a one day a week course, there's only so much she can really explain to us and prepare us for."

Guide	N/A	N/A	8	53	Would like to see clearer instruction as to what is expected of them in the field. Guidance on what to do/ what should be completed in the field.	"I know other students had raised the concern that they felt very lost and sometimes, like just left to their own devices where they weren't sure exactly what to do."
Subject	N/A	N/A	4	27	Wants more experience on a specific subject of the class. More content presented to them before applying it into the field.	"like specifically mapping, because I know at first it's really daunting to try to learn that."

Appendix C14						
Interview Q14: What aspects of this course do you think should stay the same? (Only asked in post-course interview)						
Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Labs	N/A	N/A	3	20	Labs are beneficial to their understanding of field work. (Subset of structure).	"I think the labs that we complete in the class are good to sort of prepare us for future projects."
Structure	N/A	N/A	8	53	Course structure, i.e. scheduling, material, etc., was a positive aspect of the course.	"I think the scheduling of the field trips, I feel like they're convenient and I don't really see like a reason for them to be changed."
Trip	N/A	N/A	9	60	Enjoys the field trips and would like them to remain the same. (Subset of structure).	"I thought all the trips were awesome."

Appendix C15

Interview Q15: What aspects of the course turned out to be less of a problem than you originally expected? (Only asked in post-course interview)

Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Course	N/A	N/A	9	60	Course materials such as labs, mapping, etc. were not as difficult to complete than expected.	"Honestly, the mapping wasn't even that big of an issue for me, really. I was expecting to be overwhelmed and getting lost in the mapping."
Time	N/A	N/A	2	13	Time management with other courses or obligations was not an issue for the student.	"I though making all of the trips might be a little bit difficult but it wasn't in the slightest."
Team	N/A	N/A	1	7	Working with peers did not negatively affect the students experience.	"I was worried about equal team work being done on field trips... I guess that wasn't a big issue."
Camp	N/A	N/A	3	20	Camping and being in the outdoors ended up not being as big of an issue than originally expected.	"I was a bit nervous because I had never been camping without my parents... When we were in Zzyzx, I'm like, oh this is fun."

Appendix C16

Interview Q16: What aspects of the course turned out to be a bigger problem than you originally expected? (Only asked in post-course interview)

Code	Pre-test Frequency (n)	Pre-test Frequency (%)	Post-test Frequency (n)	Post-test Frequency (%)	Explanation	Example response
Time	N/A	N/A	2	13	The timing of the field trips, or not being able to make the trip.	"I guess on the last field trip, I ended up having an online midterm... that was a bit of a problem."
Subject	N/A	N/A	9	60	Had a hard time relating to a specific class subject i.e. mapping, fault identification, etc.	"I didn't think mapping was going to be so difficult at first for me."

Phys	N/A	N/A	1	7	Being able to physically keep up with the class.	"I guess maybe just I knew we would be hiking, but just like the amount of hiking, shorter hikes, you know, maybe like a couple of hours, but it's like an entire day."
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